

METHODS OF PROMOTING ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE REGION THROUGH TAXES

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Annotation: The article examines the factors of economic growth of the region on the basis of tax incentives. Priority areas have been developed: tax incentives, the formation of an innovative economy in the region.

Key words: region, economic growth, innovation, tax system, tax burden, tax efficiency, innovation infrastructure.

Introduction. World experience shows that today innovations play an important role not only in the development of individual organizations, but also in ensuring the competitiveness of the national economy, improving the quality of life of the population and increasing its well-being. "Every year, the United States of America exports 740.0 billion, Germany 530.0 billion, and Japan 410.0 billion from the export of high-tech products. earns USD. Today, the volume of high-tech products in the world market is 2.0 trillion. 300 billion More than USD. 39% of this amount is produced by the USA, 35% by Japan, 17% by Germany, and 9% by other countries." [1] One of the main factors of successful innovative development is an effective system of state regulation and support of business entities.

In the innovative development of the economy, the state uses all economic instruments at its disposal, including fiscal, tariff, credit, insurance and other economic mechanisms. Currently, the importance and importance of innovative development of the economy by leading international financial institutions, scientific research centers, prestigious higher education and scientific institutions in developed countries, as well as the need to effectively use and improve the tax mechanism in the regulation of

scientific research and innovative activities, tax incentives and harmonious and rational use of the limitation function, increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of the tax mechanism in stimulating scientific research and experimental construction works (ITTKI), at the same time, actively attracting investments to these types of activities, increasing innovative activity and accelerating innovative processes of taxes Extensive scientific research is being conducted to strengthen its role. In recent years, consistent reforms have been implemented in our country to create a favorable tax environment for business entities. In order to create a new type of economic growth and transition to sustainable innovative development, a number of measures aimed at stimulating the innovative activities of economic entities were implemented, in which measures in the tax field were given an important place to encourage innovation. Many changes have been made to the tax legislation aimed at promotion. However, the analysis of the changes in the tax legislation showed that there is no single methodological approach to determining the category of taxpayers that should be encouraged in the adopted changes and the structure of the effective tax mechanisms used for each of them. . This indicates the need to develop a complex system of tax incentives for economic entities to actively engage in innovative activities in the innovative development of the economy and a unified methodological approach to the effective use of existing tax mechanisms.

It is known that the development of the modern economy cannot be ensured without innovations and investments. Therefore, encouraging business entities to engage in scientific research and innovative activities, to actively attract investments to these activities, and to produce innovative products is considered the main task of regulating the economy of any modern state. Among them, rapid development of the economy of Uzbekistan, increasing the flow of investments, rapid introduction of modern innovative technologies with wide application of scientific and technical achievements to economic sectors, social and other fields are very important that the state must solve today and in the near future. , is a pressing issue. The tax system is the most effective means of influencing the state in the regulation of the economy,

including the support and stimulation of innovative development. [2] Provision of innovative development based on the use of the tax mechanism is usually based on the stimulating effect of tax incentives and reliefs on the activities of innovative enterprises. At the moment, the use of taxes as a means of regulating the economy by the state is based on the use of the functions of regulation, including incentives, restrictions and compensation of taxes. The effect of the regulatory function is based on uneven taxation of various objects and categories of taxpayers. The unevenness of the tax burden, in turn, creates the desired effect. In this case, by easing the tax burden in the priority direction, the state creates more favorable conditions for economic development in this direction, and the increase in the tax burden in another direction creates additional obstacles for development.

It is worth noting that in the innovative development of the economy, not only the use of measures with the nature of incentives (reduced tax rates, tax holidays, tax deductions and other benefits), but also restrictions on entities that do not take measures to increase innovative activity (it is advisable to use mechanisms with the characteristics of increasing tax rates, introducing additional taxes, restrictions on the use of benefits) and compensating (using a zero rate). [3] The effectiveness of stimulating the innovative development of the economy by means of taxes depends first of all on the precise definition of the circle of taxpayers to whom the stimulation effect should be directed and on the set of appropriate tax mechanisms. The lack of a unified terminology related to the innovative economy and its participants significantly reduces the effectiveness of tax incentives for the innovative development of the economy. As a result of the analysis of the regulation of scientific research and innovative activities through the tax mechanism, including the analysis of the practice of incentives, it can be concluded that the objectives of the incentives are not clear, the indicators to be achieved are not defined, specific and non-specific tax benefits in the form of full exemption from taxes such as VAT, profit tax and turnover tax have been applied for the period. After all, currently, in the international experience, tax credits, tax deductions, tax holidays, reduced and differentiated tax rates are used as

instruments for effective promotion of these types of activities.[4] In addition, the analysis of the state of attraction of investments in the improvement of innovative infrastructure by means of the tax mechanism showed that the amount of funds directed to technical and technological re-equipment, the purchase of new technological equipment, after deducting the depreciation calculated in the relevant tax period, but the tax it was observed that the mechanism of reducing the taxable profit of enterprises in the amount of no more than 30% of the taxable profit has a low level of influence on the investment activity of consumers of innovative products or technology.

Therefore, instead of this mechanism, a proposal was made to introduce an investment tax deduction. The effectiveness of tax incentives and their impact on economic growth remains a problem for the state and individual organizations. Therefore, the effectiveness of tax instruments aimed at stimulating innovative development, as well as the assessment of the level of their impact on the tax burden of economic entities, the development of a system of evaluation criteria that allows determining the impact of incentives on the level of income should be considered. The increase in the scope of incentives through taxes requires attention to the problem of their efficiency. After all, the lack of a mechanism for evaluating and monitoring the results of incentive levers is one of the factors that hinders their effectiveness. This problem is complex enough to be solved. The complexity is that, firstly, in most cases, it is related to the lack of accurate and sufficient statistical data, and secondly, it is related to the uniqueness of the situation of enterprises in different economic conditions. Nevertheless, in the innovative development of the economy, the assessment of the effectiveness of tax mechanisms is of great importance. Innovative activity can be expressed as a chain of events for the purpose of innovative development of the economy through the effective use of the tax mechanism. In particular, the emergence of new knowledge (ideas).

- the transformation of an idea into an intellectual product (innovation).
- introduction of innovations into production

- commercialization of innovations (commercially successful production of an innovative product)

- consumption of innovative products.

The following three main directions of this chain can be stimulated through taxes:

- production of innovations; introducing innovations into production; consumption of innovative products.

It is possible to determine the range of entities that are required to be stimulated in the specified areas of stimulating the innovative development of the economy by means of taxes:

- innovative enterprises.

Currently, most of the tax instruments that stimulate the innovative development of the economy are focused on the activities of this category of enterprises. However, the effectiveness of stimulating the innovative development of the economy through taxes depends on the equal distribution of the stimulating effect to other categories of subjects.

Otherwise, the production of innovations, which is important for the innovative development of the economy

- implementation

- commercialization

- the consumption chain is interrupted.

- enterprises introducing innovations into production.

In our opinion, this category of subjects needs more encouragement. Because the introduction of innovations in production is the main condition for ensuring the innovative development of the economy. In addition, special incentives for innovation production lead to the possibility of exporting innovations.

- Enterprises that are consumers of innovative products. These enterprises also need tax incentives to increase demand for innovative products. Also, special promotion of consumption of innovative products leads to the possibility of importing innovative products.

- Innovative infrastructure enterprises. The inclusion of this category in the composition of entities requiring tax incentives is important for the normal functioning of the innovative economy, as the activity of innovative infrastructure enterprises is related to all stages of innovative activity.

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